

EFFECT OF MATURITY LEVELS AND SPERMINE ON PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AT LOW TEMPERATURE STORAGE OF PAPAYA CV. RED LADY TAIWAN

J. H. Gohil*, T.R. Ahlawat, H. F. Patel, A. J. Bhandari and A. I. Makwana

Agricultural Experimental Station Paria,

Horticulture Polytechnic Paria

Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari, Gujrat, India.

MS Received: 15.11.2024; MS Revised:28.12.2024; MS Accepted:29.12.2024)

MS 3332

(RESEARCH PAPER IN HORTICULTURE)

Abstract

An experiment was conducted at the Department of Fruit Science and Department of Post Harvest Technology of ASPEE College of Horticulture and Forestry, Navsari Agriculture University, Navsari during December 2014 and April 2015. The experiment comprised of harvesting papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan at three different maturity stages (Colour break stage, 50% yellow and 75% yellow stage), dipping them in aqueous solutions of spermine (0.0, 1.0 and 2.0 mM) and storing them at ambient as well as $12 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ temperature. The eighteen treatments were evaluated in a Completely Randomized with Factorial Concept (FCRD) and replicated three times. Results indicated a significant impact of maturity levels on all parameters included in the study. Postharvest application of spermine @ 2.0 mM had a significant influence on all traits studied in this investigation. When considered individually, twenty five percent mature fruits had maximum fruit weight, peel weight, pulp weight, peel to pulp ratio and fruit firmness when treated with. Significant differences were observed in physical parameters due to storage temperature. Between the two temperatures, storage at $12 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ temperature resulted in higher fruit weight, peel weight, pulp weight and pulp to peel ratio.

Key words - Red Lady Taiwan, maturity stages,

Introduction

Papaya is native to tropical America and is believed to have originated from South America (De Candolle, 1884). It was introduced in India in the early part of the 16th century from Philippines through Malaysia (Schroeder, 1958). It belongs to the family Caricaceae which consists of six relatively small genera. Papaya is highly appreciated worldwide for its flavour, nutritional qualities, digestive properties and serotonin content (Fernandes *et al.*, 2006). Papaya is a good source of serotonin (0.99 mg/100 mg), which has been associated with enabling the gut to mediate reflex activity and also decreasing the risk of thrombosis (Santiago-Silva *et al.*, 2011). Leaves of *Carica papaya* are able to remove stains. Papain has milk clotting (rennet) and protein digesting properties. A piece of raw papaya is often added, when preparing meat. The papain present in raw papaya not only reduces the time taken for cooking meat but also makes the meat very tender. Value added products like juice, blended beverages, jam, jelly, *petha*, *tuty phooty*, dehydrated, osmo dried, cereal flakes, fruit bar, candy, restructured and intermediate moisture and frozen products can be developed from fresh papaya fruits. The pectin content in papaya fruits facilitates jam preparation and easy setting. Gujarat is the second largest producer of papaya in the country.

Material And Methods

The experiment was carried out during December 2014 and April 2015 at the Department of Post Harvest Technology, ASPEE College of Horticulture and Forestry, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari, which is situated on the coast of Arabian sea at $20^\circ\text{-}57'$ N latitude and $72^\circ\text{-}54'$ longitude at an altitude of about 10-12 meters above the mean sea level. The campus is 13 km away from Dandi, a historical place near the Arabian seashore.

Treatment Details**Factor- 1 (Maturity stages)**

M₁- Colour break stage (25% yellow)

M₂- ½ of the skin is yellow (50% yellow)

M₃- ¾ of the skin is yellow (75% yellow)

Factor-2 (Spermine treatments)

S₀- 0.0 mM spermine

S₁- 1.0 mM spermine

S₂- 2.0 mM spermine

Factor- 3 (Storage Temperature)

T₁ - Ambient Temperature (December-2014 26.2°C and April-2015 27.2°C)

T₂ - Low Temperature ($12 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$)

Uniformly sized papaya fruits harvested at different maturity stages were dipped in aqueous solutions of spermine for 5 minutes and dried for 30 minutes at room temperature and packed in rigid plastic crates and kept at a temperature of $12 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ as well as room temperature.

Physical observations recorded**Fruit weight (g)**

From each treatment, three uniformly sized fruits were weighed on electronic balance and the average value was computed.

Peel weight (%)

Three uniformly sized fruits were selected from each treatment and peeled using a peeler. The peel weight was measured on an electronic balance and expressed in grams.

Pulp weight (%)

Three uniformly sized fruits were selected from each treatment. Fruits were cut vertically, seeds were removed and the pulp was extracted. The pulp was weighed on an electronic balance and expressed in grams.

Pulp:Peel ratio

The pulp:peel ratio was calculated by dividing the pulp weight by the peel weight of three uniformly sized papaya fruits.

Fruit firmness (kg/cm²)

Fruit firmness was tested by means of a pocket penetrometer (Italy made, fruit tester, model FT 327). A circular thin patch of skin about one cm in diameter was removed from the fruit surface with the help of a sharp knife and the penetrometer (adjusted to zero) was pierced into the fruit up to the knob. The pressure required to penetrate flesh penetrometer was recorded in kg/cm² provided on the circular disk of the pocket penetrometer.

The data collected were analyzed statistically as per the procedure appropriate for Completely Randomized Design with Factorial Concept (FCRD). The treatment means were compared by means of critical differences at 5 per cent level of probability and the data was analyzed statistically (Panse and Sukhatme, 1967).

Results And Discussion**Effect of maturity levels**

There was a significant influence of various maturity levels on fruit weight, peel weight, pulp weight and pulp to peel ratio of papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan (Table 1). Twenty five percent mature fruits had the maximum fruit weight, peel weight, pulp weight and pulp to peel ratio on the 8th day of storage. Fruits harvested at 25% maturity had lower PLW and respiration rate which may have contributed to higher fruit weight, peel weight and pulp weight in these fruits. A higher pulp to peel ratio was the result of higher pulp weight in relation to peel weight in the treated fruits. Maturity levels had a significant effect on fruit firmness in papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan. Fruit firmness was the highest in fruits twenty five percent mature fruits on the 8th day of storage. Firmness showed a declining trend as the maturity level progressed. Possibly the enzymes related to softening were still not completely synthesized and activated in 25% mature fruits. In addition, the quantity of ethylene receptors is reduced in fruits harvested when

still green (Trewavas, 1982). This is in agreement with earlier findings of Bron and Jacomino (2006) and Serry *et al.* (2011) in papaya, Alhassan *et al.* (2014) in sweet orange cv. Late Valencia and Gonge *et al.* (2014) in banana.

Effect of spermine

In the current investigation, spermine at a higher level proved more effective in improving the shelf life and quality parameters of papaya. There was a significant influence of spermine on fruit weight, peel weight, pulp weight and pulp to peel ratio of papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan. Spermine 2.0 mM resulted in the maximum fruit weight, pulp weight and pulp to peel ratio on the 8th day of storage. The maximum fruit weight, pulp weight and peel weight can be attributed to the lower PLW and respiration rate of these fruits. Spermine had a significant effect on fruit firmness in papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan. Fruit firmness was the highest in fruits treated with 2.0 mM on the 8th of storage. Softening of fruits is caused either by the breakdown of insoluble protopectins into soluble pectins or by the cellular disintegration leading increased membrane permeability (Mattoo *et al.*, 1975). The effect of polyamines on maintaining fruit firmness can be attributed to their cross linkage to –COO- group of pectic substances in the cell wall, resulting in rigidification, detected immediately after treatment. This binding also blocks the access of degrading enzymes, such as pectinmethylesterase, pectinesterase and polygalacturonase, reducing the rate of firmness (Valero *et al.*, 2002). The results on fruit firmness in the present study are in agreement with the findings of Basiouny (1996) in blueberry, Romero *et al.* (2001) in apricot, Khan *et al.* (2007) in plum, Malik *et al.* (2006) and Bhat *et al.* (2014) in mango and Champa *et al.* (2015) in grape.

Effect of storage temperature

There was a significant influence of storage temperature on fruit weight, pulp weight and pulp to peel ratio of papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan. Fruits stored at low temperature had higher fruit weight, pulp weight and pulp to peel ratio on the 8th day of storage. The reduction in weight of fruits in storage was attributed to the physiological loss in weight due to respiration, transpiration and other biological changes taking place in the fruits (Thin *et al.*, 2013). Fruits stored at low temperature had minimum PLW which may have resulted in higher fruit weight. Greater pulp to peel ratio at lower temperature can be attributed to lower weight loss and higher water content (Ahmad *et al.*, 2001). Higher pulp to peel ratio in papaya at lower temperature was earlier recorded by Bariya (2012). Storage temperature had a significant effect on the fruit firmness in papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan. Fruit firmness was higher in fruits stored at low temperature on the 8th day of storage. The increased softness of ripe fruits at higher temperature was due to the greater starch hydrolysis and greater weight loss during ripening (Ahmad *et al.*, 2001). Premrata (2009) and Bariya (2012) in papaya; Miller and McDonald (1999) Rivera-Lopez *et al.* (2005) and Caron *et al.* (2013) in papaya, Arnel and Rio (2004) in persimmon and Thin *et al.* (2013) in mango are in agreement with above findings.

Conclusion

The maximum fruit weight, peel weight, pulp weight, pulp to peel ratio and fruit firmness in twenty five percent mature fruits on the 8th day of storage. Fruits treated with 2.0 mM spermine recorded minimum peel weight on the 8th day of storage. The maximum fruit weight, pulp weight, pulp to peel ratio, fruit firmness, were observed in the treatment comprising 2.0 mM spermine on the 8th day of storage. Storage at 12±1°C temperature resulted in the highest fruit weight, peel weight, pulp weight, pulp : peel ratio and fruit firmness after 8th days of storage.

References

1. Ahmad, Saeed, Thompson, A.K., Ahmad, Ishfaq, Hafiz and Ali, Ashghar (2001). Effect of temperature on the ripening behavior and quality of banana fruit. *Int. J. of Agric. & Bio.*, **3** (2): 224-227.
2. Alam, M.S., Hossain, M.M., Ara, M.I., Amanullah, A.S.M. and Mondal, M.F. (2010). Effect of packaging materials and

growth regulators on quality and shelf life of papaya. *Bangladesh Res. Pub. J.*, **3** (3): 1052-1061.

3. Alam, M.S., Hossain, M.M., Ara, M.I., Amanullah, A.S.M. and Mondal, M.F. (2010). Effect of packaging materials and growth regulators on quality and shelf life of papaya. *Bangladesh Res. Pub. J.*, **3** (3): 1052-1061.
4. Alhassan, A. F. and Adjei, P. Y. (2014). Effect of maturity stage and storage duration on physico-chemical properties of citrus (*Citrus sinensis* var. Late Valencia). *European Sci. J.*, **10** (36): 148-162.
5. Arnel, L. and Rio, M. A .D. (2004). Quality of persimmon fruit cv. Rojo Brillante during storage at different temperatures. *Spanish J. Agri. Res.*, **2** (2): 243-247.
6. Bariya, P. J. (2012). Effect of ripening retardants and storage conditions on shelf life of papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) cv. Red Lady Taiwan. M. Sc. (Horti.) thesis submitted to Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari.
7. Basiouny, F. M. (1996). Blueberry fruit quality and storability influenced by post-harvest application of polyamines and heat treatments. *Proc. Fla. State Hort. Soc.*, **109**: 269-272.
8. Bhat, A., Kaul, R. J., Reshi, M. and Gupta, N. (2014). Effect of polyamines on shelf life and chilling injury of mango cv. Dashehari. *The Bioscan*, **9** (3): 1097-1100.
9. Bron, H. U. and Jacomino, P. (2006). Ripening and quality of 'Golden' papaya fruit harvested at different maturity stages. *Braz. J. Plant Physiol.*, **18** (3): 389-396.
10. Caron, V. C., Chitolina, G. M. and Jacomino, A. P. (2013). Influence of low temperature storage on the postharvest quality of papaya fruit (*Carica papaya* L.). *Proc. Fla. State Hort. Soc.*, **126**: 200-202.
11. Champa, Harindra W. A., Gill, M. I. S., Mahajan, B. V. C. and Bedi Seema (2015). Exogenous treatment of spermine to maintain quality and extend postharvest life of table grapes (*Vitis vinifera* L.) cv. Flame Seedless under low temperature storage. *Food Sci. and Tech.*, **60**: 412-415.
12. De Candolle, A. (1884). *Origin of Cultivated Plants*. London.
13. Fernandes, F. A. N., Rodrigues, S., Odisseia, C. P. and Oliveira, E. L. (2006). Optimization of osmotic dehydration of papaya followed by air-drying. *Food Res. Int.*, **39** (4): 492-498.
14. Gonge, A. P., Patel, N. L., Ahlawat, T. R. and Patil, S. J. (2014). Influence of harvesting maturity and low temperature storage on shelf life and quality of banana cv. Grand Naine. *Indian J. Hort.*, **71** (3): 441-445.
15. Khan, A. S., Singh, Z. and Abbasi, N. A. (2007). Pre-storage putrescine application suppresses ethylene biosynthesis and retards fruit softening during low temperature storage in 'Angelo' plum. *Postharvest Biol. Technol.*, **46**: 36-46.
16. Malik, A. U., Singh, Z. and Tan, S. C. (2006). Exogenous application of polyamines improve shelf life and fruit quality of mango. *Acta. Hort.*, **699**.
17. Mattoo, A. K., Murata, T., Pantastico, E. B., Chachin, K. Ogata, K. and Phan, C. T. (1975). Chemical changes during ripening and senescence. In: *Post-Harvest Physiology Handling and Utilization of Tropical and Subtropical Fruits and Vegetables*, Pantastico E B (Ed.). AVI publication, Westport, Connecticut, pp. 103-27.
18. Miller, W. R. and McDonald, R. E. (1999). Irrigation, stage of maturity at harvest, and storage temperature during ripening affect papaya fruit quality. *Hort. Sci.*, **34** (6): 1112-1115.
19. Panse, V. G. and Sukhatme, P. V. (1967). *Statistical Methods for Agricultural Workers*. ICAR pub., New Delhi.

20. **Premlata. (2009).** Post harvest management of papaya cv. Taiwan Red Lady. M. Sc. (Horti.) thesis submitted to Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari.
21. **Rivera-Lopez, J., Vazquez-Ortiz, F. A., Ayala-Zavala, J. F., Sotelo-Mundo, R. R. and Gonzalez-Aguilar, G. A. (2005).** Cutting shape and storage temperature affect overall quality of fresh cut papaya cv. 'Maradol'. *J. Food Sci.*, **70**: 482-489.
22. **Santiago-Silva, P., Labanca, R. A., Reneta, A. and Beatriz A. Gloria (2011).** Functional potential of tropical fruits with respect to free bioactive amines. *Food Res. Int.*, **44** (5): 1264-1268.
23. **Schroeder, C. A. (1958).** The origin, spread and improvement of avocado, sapodilla and papaya. *Indian. J. Hort.*, **15** (3): 263-66.
24. **Serry, N. K. H. (2011).** Post harvest handling of solo papaya fruits harvested at different maturity stages. *Ame. Eru. J. Agric. Env. Sci.*, **11** (2): 205-210.
25. **Thinh, D. C., Uthaibutra, J. and Joomwong, A. (2013).** Effect of storage temperatures on ripening behavior and quality change of Vietnamese mango cv. 'Cat Hoa Lac'. *Int. J. Biotech.*, **3** (3): 19-30.
26. **Trewavas, A. J. (1982).** Growth substance sensitivity: the limiting factor in plant development. *Physiol. Plant*, **55**: 60-72.

Table 1. Effect of maturity levels, spermine and low temperature on physiological weight loss (%) and respiration rate (mg CO₂/kg/hr) of papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan.

Treatments	Physiological loss in weight (%)						Respiration rate (mg CO ₂ /kg/hr)					
	4 th day			8 th day			4 th day			8 th day		
	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled
Maturity levels												
M₁	2.05	2.13	2.09	4.20	4.29	4.25	42.68	43.04	42.86	46.91	45.20	46.05
M₂	2.46	2.58	2.52	4.46	4.39	4.43	43.06	45.23	44.14	54.87	56.68	55.77
M₃	2.47	2.40	2.43	4.89	4.80	4.85	47.75	49.31	48.53	56.43	53.98	55.20
S. Em. ±	0.009	0.014	0.008	0.012	0.011	0.008	0.326	0.201	0.190	0.439	0.413	0.299
CD at 5%	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.93	0.58	0.54	1.26	1.18	0.84
Spermine												
S₀	2.45	2.54	2.50	4.47	4.59	4.53	49.22	52.38	50.80	52.13	54.17	53.15
S₁	2.26	2.37	2.31	4.48	4.40	4.44	43.87	45.12	44.49	55.69	50.86	53.27
S₂	2.17	2.08	2.13	4.40	4.56	4.48	46.41	42.48	44.44	50.50	52.57	51.54
S. Em. ±	0.009	0.014	0.007	0.012	0.011	0.007	0.326	0.201	0.263	0.439	0.413	0.426
CD at 5%	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.93	0.58	0.75	1.26	1.18	1.22
Temperature												
T₁	2.50	2.39	2.46	5.40	5.48	5.44	65.56	60.89	63.22	67.17	69.35	51.30
T₂	2.26	2.18	2.22	3.53	3.68	3.60	22.43	24.56	23.49	33.54	35.44	34.49
S. Em. ±	0.01	0.012	0.007	0.01	0.009	0.007	0.27	0.164	0.155	0.364	0.337	0.244
CD at 5%	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.86	0.67	0.76	1.03	0.97	1.00
CV %	2.65	2.36	3.14	3.12	3.04	3.07	3.06	2.88	2.97	3.64	3.42	3.51
Interaction												
T×M	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.05	1.38	0.88	1.13	1.78	1.80	1.79
T×S	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.05	1.38	0.88	1.13	1.78	1.72	1.75
M×S	0.04	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.06	1.62	1.20	1.41	2.18	2.13	2.14
T×M×S	0.06	0.10	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	2.29	1.80	2.04	3.08	2.95	3.01

Table2. Effect of maturity levels, spermine and low temperature on fruit weight (g) and peel weight (g) of papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan.

Treatments	Fruit weight (g)						Peel weight (g)					
	4 th day			8 th day			4 th day			8 th day		
	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled
Maturity levels												
M ₁	1065.66	1075.13	1070.395	1010.41	998.31	1004.36	78.23	79.12	78.18	74.88	73.63	74.25
M ₂	1048.71	1029.41	1039.06	964.77	972.87	968.82	78.11	78.78	78.44	72.32	74.13	73.22
M ₃	1016.22	1007.83	1012.025	948.79	923.11	935.95	76.38	77.01	76.69	70.83	71.92	71.37
S. Em. ±	8.936	8.439	6.103	6.216	7.340	4.776	0.646	0.524	0.58	0.589	0.406	0.49
CD at 5%	25.65	24.22	17.21	17.84	21.06	13.47	1.85	1.50	1.71	1.69	1.17	1.43
Spermine												
S ₀	1043.38	1051.20	1047.29	941.42	972.11	956.76	78.70	77.83	78.26	70.83	71.92	71.37
S ₁	1058.41	1081.32	1069.86	967.32	982.18	974.75	78.28	77.52	77.90	72.07	72.86	72.46
S ₂	1094.32	1112.87	1103.59	991.84	1010.38	1001.11	77.83	78.12	77.97	70.58	72.94	71.76
S. Em. ±	8.936	8.439	4.983	6.216	7.340	3.900	0.646	0.524	0.585	0.589	0.406	0.497
CD at 5%	25.65	24.22	14.05	17.84	21.06	11.00	3.77	3.25	3.51	3.65	3.46	3.55
Temperature												
T ₁	1070.39	1057.22	1063.805	972.14	956.32	964.23	77.34	76.86	77.10	68.43	69.32	68.87
T ₂	1138.20	1118.33	1128.265	1034.12	1057.71	1045.915	78.83	80.23	79.53	75.83	75.02	75.42
S. Em. ±	7.30	6.890	4.983	5.08	5.993	3.900	0.534	0.428	0.481	0.482	0.332	0.407
CD at 5%	20.94	19.77	14.05	14.57	17.20	11.00	1.51	1.23	1.37	1.38	0.95	1.16
CV %	3.72	3.61	3.64	2.78	3.39	3.07	2.77	3.05	2.91	3.25	3.42	3.33
Interaction												
T×M	36.27	34.25	24.34	25.23	29.79	19.05	2.62	2.13	2.37	2.39	1.65	2.02
T×S	36.27	34.25	24.34	25.23	29.79	19.05	2.62	2.13	2.37	2.39	1.65	2.02
M×S	44.42	41.95	29.81	30.90	36.48	23.33	3.21	2.60	2.90	2.93	2.02	2.47
T×M×S	62.82	59.32	42.16	43.70	51.59	32.99	4.54	3.68	4.11	4.14	2.86	3.50

Table 3. Effect of maturity levels, spermine and low temperature on pulp weight (g), Pulp : Peel ratio and fruit firmness (kg/cm²) of papaya cv. Red Lady Taiwan.

Treatments	Pulp weight (g)						Pulp : Peel ratio						Fruit Firmness (kg/cm ²)					
	4 th day			8 th day			4 th day			8 th day			4 th day			8 th day		
	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled	2014	2015	Pooled
Maturity levels																		
M ₁	947.04	913.27	930.15	900.15	867.84	883.99	12.12	11.94	12.03	12.02	11.78	11.90	3.95	3.85	3.90	3.05	3.17	3.11
M ₂	932.48	913.39	922.93	856.45	865.00	860.72	11.92	11.98	11.95	11.84	11.66	11.75	3.80	3.86	3.83	2.94	2.89	2.92
M ₃	899.84	891.54	895.69	831.16	810.19	820.67	11.78	11.67	11.72	11.63	11.26	11.55	3.73	3.63	3.68	2.14	2.20	2.17
S. Em. ±	4.004	4.640	4.322	5.546	6.860	6.08	0.055	0.045	0.050	0.072	0.105	0.089	0.022	0.019	0.014	0.009	0.009	0.006
CD at 5%	11.72	13.60	12.66	16.49	19.69	18.09	0.15	0.13	0.14	0.20	0.30	0.25	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.02
Spermine																		
S ₀	925.54	934.88	930.21	836.35	866.88	851.61	11.89	11.96	11.92	11.84	11.89	11.86	3.72	3.82	3.76	2.86	2.69	2.78
S ₁	944.71	962.79	953.75	862.25	876.60	869.42	12.06	12.26	12.16	11.96	12.07	12.01	3.75	3.80	3.78	2.90	2.70	2.80
S ₂	980.04	998.34	989.19	885.02	892.03	888.52	12.45	12.41	12.43	12.15	12.33	12.24	3.96	3.83	3.89	2.93	2.76	2.84
S. Em. ±	4.084	4.740	4.412	5.746	6.860	6.303	0.080	0.056	0.068	0.072	0.105	0.089	0.022	0.019	0.012	0.009	0.009	0.005
CD at 5%	11.72	13.60	12.66	16.49	19.69	18.09	0.15	0.13	0.14	0.20	0.30	0.25	0.06	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.01
Temperature																		
T ₁	974.21	964.23	969.22	856.32	876.32	866.32	12.37	12.51	12.44	12.32	12.36	12.34	3.12	3.02	3.07	1.39	1.47	1.43
T ₂	1062.54	1059.87	1061.20	961.89	957.57	959.73	12.96	12.76	12.86	12.68	12.65	12.66	4.65	4.53	4.59	3.60	3.73	3.67
S. Em. ±	3.331	3.870	3.601	4.69	5.601	5.146	0.073	0.038	0.055	0.059	0.086	0.072	0.02	0.016	0.012	0.01	0.007	0.005
CD at 5%	9.57	11.11	10.34	13.46	16.07	14.76	0.20	0.11	0.15	0.17	0.24	0.20	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01
CV %	2.80	2.88	2.84	3.38	3.80	3.59	2.85	2.48	2.66	2.67	4.02	3.34	2.41	2.12	2.25	2.62	2.77	2.68
Interaction																		
T×M	16.57	19.24	17.90	23.32	27.84	25.58	0.36	0.19	0.27	0.29	0.42	0.36	0.09	0.08	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.02
T×S	16.57	19.24	17.90	23.32	27.84	25.58	0.36	0.19	0.28	0.29	0.42	0.36	0.09	0.08	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.02
M×S	20.30	23.56	21.93	28.56	34.10	31.33	0.44	0.23	0.33	0.36	0.52	0.43	0.11	0.09	0.07	0.04	0.04	0.02
T×M×S	28.71	33.32	31.03	40.39	48.22	44.30	0.62	0.33	0.47	0.51	0.74	0.62	0.15	0.13	0.10	0.06	0.06	0.02